

Deliverable D5.1 (D19)

Advertising of all ESR positions

30/01/2019

RNAct MSCA-ITN project 813239

Dissemination level: Public

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The RNAct project

RNAct is a EU-MSCA ITN project with as research aim the design of novel **RNA recognition motif (RRM)** proteins for exploitation in synthetic biology and bio-analytics. We use **computational approaches** to analyse proteins and RNA, and test newly designed RRM in large-scale experiments. Viable RRM are studied with integrative **structural biology**, and will be applied in **synthetic biology** and in **bio-analytics**.

See <http://rnact.eu/> for more information.

Project partners

(Coordinator)

(Academic)

(Commercial)

About this document

This reports deliverable D5.1 (D19) of the RNAct MSCA-ITN project. It was prepared by:

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 813239. The responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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Advertising of all ESR positions

The description of the 10 ESR positions was discussed with all partners, and a general advertisement for the whole project written and distributed (see Supporting information). The end date for applications was set for the 15th of March 2019.

The positions were first advertised on EURAXESS on 20th of December 2018, before the start of the project. The original plan was to advertise earlier, but we wanted to ensure that i) all relevant information was available online via the project website:

<http://rnact.eu/>

and that ii) a centralized site was available for receiving the applications:

<https://wvranken.wufoo.com/forms/zjepab507unqzd/>

The original EURAXESS advert is available from:

<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/365178>

The ESR positions were then also advertised on the following sites:

- ISCB: <https://careers.iscb.org/jobs/view/6461>
- Naturejobs: <https://www.nature.com/naturecareers/job?id=672279>
- ScienceCareers: <https://jobs.sciencecareers.org/previewjob/491389/10-international-phd-positions-in-protein-design-for-synthetic-biology/>
- University positions: <https://www.universitypositions.eu/job/592lu/10-international-phd-positions-in-protein-design-for-synthetic-biology>
- The Guardian: <https://jobs.theguardian.com/job/6844979/10-international-phd-positions-in-protein-design-for-synthetic-biology/?LinkSource=PremiumListing>
- Glassdoor: <https://nl.glassdoor.be/Job/jobs.htm?typedKeyword=rnact&sc.keyword=rnact>
- ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/job/926518_10_international_PhD_positions_in_protein_design_for_synthetic_biology

Further advertising was done locally by all partners, for example:

<http://www.csic.es/contratos-predoctorales>

<https://www.sfbf.fr/content/knowledge-based-modeling-and-design-rna-binding-protein>

<https://www.sfbf.fr/content/fragment-based-protein-rna-docking-protein-design>

<https://members.loria.fr/IsaureCB/jobs-available/phd/>

<http://www.loria.fr/fr/emplois/phd-a-new-specific-knowledge-base-for-modeling-and-design-of-rna-binding-proteins/>

<http://www.loria.fr/fr/emplois/phd-rna-protein-docking-by-combinatorial-assembly-for-protein-design/>

There are currently 50 applications with still 1 ½ month to go. At the kick-off meeting (Brussels, 31/01/2019) the beneficiaries discussed the recruitment in detail, and devised more strategies to increase the number of applications. We will continue to advertise locally, especially targeting mailing lists with specific professional interests (*e.g.* the Benelux Bioinformatics Conference mailing list). We will also use more detailed descriptions of the relevant ESR positions for these mailing lists, while referring to the general application form. In addition, we will continue to advertise more broadly for all 10 positions. We will then assess the quality and number of applications halfway February, by which time we aim to have several hundred of applications, and will continue to advertise at other sites if necessary.

Supporting information

Original 1-page advertisement

10 international PhD positions in protein design for synthetic biology.

These positions are provided by RNAct, a **European Innovative Training Network** project. The interdisciplinary research aim of RNAct is the design of novel **RNA recognition motif (RRM) proteins** for exploitation in **synthetic biology and bio-analytics**. This includes computational approaches at the sequence and structure levels of proteins and RNA, large-scale phage display experiments with RNA screening, integrative structural biology approaches, implementation of RRM in synthetic biology, and bio-analytics to detect RNA in-cell and design RNA biochips.

RNAct is a collaborative project between 7 teams in 6 countries, from both academia and biotech industry, that will offer a comprehensive and cross-disciplinary structured curriculum for doctoral students. **10 doctoral thesis fellowships** (for **ESRs**, Early-Stage Researchers) are available in the areas of structural bioinformatics, structural biology using NMR and crystallography, synthetic biology and bio-analytics.

Eligible applicants **must hold a Masters degree of Science (MSc)** in the field of chemistry, biochemistry, physical, life sciences or computational sciences as requested in the respective job description. They must not have stayed in the country of the host lab for more than 1 year during the last 3 years, and be in **the first four years (full-time equivalent) of their research careers**. Do not apply if you already hold a Ph.D.

Further information: <http://rnact.eu>

Contact and information: e-mail to info@rnact.eu

Applications must be submitted online at <https://tinyurl.com/rnact-eu>

Deadline for applications: 15/03/2019

ESR1: Predicting biophysical characteristics of proteins from their amino acid sequence (Computational, VUB, Brussels, Belgium)

ESR2: Improving the in-silico structure representation of proteins (Computational, VUB, Brussels, Belgium)

ESR3: Collect, integrate and analyse RRM data (Computational, CNRS, Nancy, France)

ESR4: Improve methods to dock RNA with proteins (Computational, CNRS, Nancy, France)

ESR5: Structure calculation and computational design of RRM (Computational/Experimental, HMGU, Munich, Germany)

ESR6: Structural biology (NMR, X-ray crystallography) and biophysical techniques of designed RRM (Experimental, HMGU, Munich, Germany)

ESR7: Analyse RRM dynamics via structural biology (NMR) and biophysical techniques (Experimental, Giotto Biotech, Florence, Italy)

ESR8: Integrate RRM in prokaryotes to create new pathways in synthetic biology (Experimental, CSIC, Valencia, Spain)

ESR9: Create biochips to study RRM/RNA interactions. (Experimental, Dynamic Biosensors, Munich, Germany)

ESR10: Deploy RRM for in-cell analytics (Experimental, Ridgeview Instruments, Uppsala, Sweden)